

Home Schooling –Advantages and Disadvantages

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ABSTRACT

Homeschooling has become a controversial issue in recent years. Homeschooling opponents opine that it is not an alternative pathway for education alongside the standard public educational system because there are still many flaws existing in this system. Homeschooling is not an effective approach to provide children with education due to scarcities of qualified educators, homeschooled children unable to well-develop their social life as well as parents have to invest massive time and dedication. Parents act as arbitrator in their children's education. They hope that through homeschooling they can convey the message they want to for their children. In reality, homeschooling is not as easy as they think. It takes decades to judge the success of their choice. Therefore, homeschooling is a high risk venture. According to Ray (2002), there are approximately 1.6-2.0 million children being taught under homeschooling by their parents. Homeschooled families grow at estimated rate of 7-15 percent per year. According to the statistics of HSLDA (2010), the main reason parents choose homeschooling is religious conviction, which is about 49%; 15% agree that homeschooling can provide a positive social environment; 14% are for academic excellence; 12% choose homeschooling because of their children's specific needs; and 5% are for flexibility and curriculum choice. The advantages to homeschooling range in scope and effect. It depends upon the person teaching, their circumstances and their ability. The advantages also rely on the characteristics or nature of the student or students involved.

INTRODUCTION

Homeschooling is home-based learning that provides an education customized to suit your child and family. It does not have to look just like school, taught at home; nor do you have to follow a typical school schedule. Homeschooling affords a family the chance to ensure that children are taught in the manner in which they learn best, offering a lot of freedom in guiding your child's education. More than just an educational choice, homeschooling typically represents a lifestyle choice for families.

Why Choose Homeschooling?

Why do families choose homeschooling? There are as many reasons to home school as there are families choosing homeschooling—and families frequently find that their reasons change as their children grow older. Homeschooling can offer something different than school. For some parents, that difference might be a more rigorous academic approach than they find at their local school. For another family, that difference might be the chance to provide their child with a broader range of educational experiences. A third family might prefer the benefits of a family focus on education, especially when their children are quite young. Yet another family may find that homeschooling allows their very active child the chance to learn without having to sit still—so that the child who hated school blossoms when brought home to learn.

Where Does Homeschooling Take Place?

Homeschooling is home-based in that it comes from the home, but frequently much of a homeschooled child's learning may take place in the community—taking advantage of the great outdoors for science and nature study, visiting museums, going on field trips, and doing volunteer work. Homeschooled children still participate in the same kinds of activities as other school children—scouting and 4-H, music and martial arts lessons, sports, dance, and art.

Contrary to some stereotypes, homeschooled children are typically not isolated at home. They usually have rich and varied lives, with more opportunities to interact with people of all ages than many children who spend their days in age-segregated classrooms.

Common Reasons to Home school

Let's explore some of the common reasons to home school.

Allows a Child to Learn at His or Her Own Pace

Homeschooling can allow each child to learn at his or her own pace, whether that happens to be faster or slower than a typical school schedule. A child might speed ahead in one area and lag behind in another, but homeschooling can adjust to provide enough challenges in your child's strengths while giving extra help and support in areas where your child might struggle. Homeschooling can also help meet the needs of children with disabilities of one kind or another.

Allows a Child to Follow Passions and Talents

Homeschooling can allow a child to follow passions and talents. Learning can fit around music lessons, sports practice, games, and performances. A child who is keenly interested in a specific subject can study other subjects through that lens—for instance, a child who loves math can study the flow of mathematical knowledge through history, can read about mathematicians and their discoveries, can write about mathematics, and delight in the mathematical underpinnings of science.

Allows Families to Educate According to Their Personal Faith, Philosophy, and Values

Homeschooling can allow families to educate according to their personal faith, philosophy, and values. Some families choose homeschooling primarily because it allows them to incorporate their

faith into their child's education or to use a faith-based curriculum.

Allows Families to Follow Unusual Schedules, Seasonal Work, and Mobile Lifestyles

Homeschooling can allow families to follow unusual schedules, seasonal work, and mobile lifestyles. Some homeschooling families take advantage of the freedom that homeschooling offers to accompany a parent with work-related travels; some families have a mobile lifestyle as performers or travelers. I've met one homeschooling family who travels the seas on board a private boat where dad is employed as the ship's captain—you can't find opportunities like that one in a classroom.

How Does Homeschooling Work—Types of Home school Programs

Traditional Programs

In a traditional program, families normally keep a structure mirrored in a school setting, meaning that they buy curriculum, textbooks, tests, teacher guides, and schedules. Traditional homeschooling parents then work with each child for a period of time on each subject to help teach the lessons and give quizzes, test, and writing assignments. Traditional homeschooling can require a lot of hands-on teaching and overseeing for you as the parent, but many families love the flexibility of working their kids' schedule around everyday life. Traditional homeschooling also allows you to purchase curriculum that fits your child's needs and your teaching style. But, it also means the burden of record keeping, grading, keeping track of credits, and making sure your children master what they need to know to succeed is on you. If you find it difficult to keep track of all the record keeping and grading materials, think about sharing that responsibility with an accredited home school academy for their expert advice and direction.

Online Home school Programs

When you're wondering how home schooling work, online programs can seem pretty daunting. Many families appreciate online learning to build their child's 21st century skills while not requiring quite as much teaching on your part. Many online home school programs have pre-recorded videos that students can watch and re-watch until they learn the content. And the tests and quizzes are graded

immediately, giving you the ability to know exactly how your child is progressing at any given time. Just be aware that some online programs are not as flexible as they have specified login times or live classes that your child will need to schedule into their school day. Good online home school programs will have note-taking guides to keep you and your kids on track as well as an Academic Advisor to help you with what's required and answer any questions you may have. Also, the best online programs will be with accredited schools to ensure that you'll get credit for what your students do during high school!

Blended Learning Programs

In essence, blended learning is a term used to describe when kids learn both online and with traditional curriculum. This option gives even more customization to students because it offers more variety in classes to best meet their learning styles and abilities. Essentially, you get the best of both worlds with blended learning! It also gives you as the parent more freedom to teach subjects you love and enjoy but choosing an online expert for subjects you are not comfortable teaching. Not sure how to teach and give labs for Biology? Stressed about correctly teaching Algebra or Geometry? No worries! There are many interactive online options with experts to teach, give assignments, and even help grade so that your child can get the very best. The best blended learning programs will choose curriculum and lessons based on your child's learning style. So, if you're not sure how your child learns best, you should take this learning style assessment before choosing a blended learning program.

Unschooling

Many parents who ask the question "how does homeschooling work" are drawn to the idea of flexibility and unique learning experiences, but wonder how to make it all come together with a curriculum. Some choose not to! Unschooling is a method where families allow their children to learn through their personal interests and build life experiences around those interests. Many parents desire for their child to enjoy learning and believe that the more personal the learning is, the more their child will retain the knowledge and desire to learn in the future. The focus then becomes encouraging exploration and learning through non-traditional methods like traveling, household responsibilities, elective classes, jobs/internships, extra-curricular

activities, and play, in which the student initiates what he/ she is learning. The heart of unschooling is allowing the child to learn based upon what interests them most rather than pre-conceived ideas of what has to be learned at each age.

List of Advantages of Homeschooling

1. It gives more freedom in planning a curriculum and schedule

Most states in the United States allow homeschooled kids to learn what they want, when they want, and for as long as they want. This means that kids can spend more hours learning subjects that really interest them, or more time can be devoted on lessons they find most difficult. There is no pressure to keep up with classmates or the tendency to feel insecure if they can't memorize their multiplication tables as fast as the other kids. Parents can also include subjects that are not typically taught in school but which they want to teach their children, such as a certain religion or their own cultural heritage and language. Additionally, you won't have to limit learning to books. You can incorporate other forms of instruction, like online courses and hands-on DIY projects.

2. It provides more personalized one-on-one learning opportunities

One problem with classroom learning in schools is there is just one teacher for quite a large number of students. And with just limited time for each class every day, some kids may not receive the attention or guidance they need to learn as best they can. With homeschooling, you can focus on each child and adapt your teaching methods to each one's best learning style.

3. It allows you to spend more time with your family

You can share the common, everyday joys of life together and not miss out on important developmental stages of each person. Parents can also journey with their children as they go through challenging times. Research shows that destructive or rebellious behavior diminishes when teenagers start homeschooling.

4. It lets you protect your children from negative influences they may encounter outside the home

Sensitive issues can be discussed when you feel they are ready to learn about them. In addition, there is

lesser tendency of their involvement in school gangs, violence, bullying, peer pressure, and other potential problems students face in school.

5. It makes family trips and vacations easier to plan.

There won't be semestral breaks and permanent daily class schedules that you need to strictly follow so you can go holiday any time of the year, and you can even make these trips.

List of Disadvantages of Homeschooling

1. It requires you to be with your kids

You will have little respite and less time for yourself or your spouse. However, some families don't mind being together all the time.

2. It consumes a lot of time, energy, and resources

If you are not a teacher by profession, you might need to exert more effort in learning about lesson preparation and teaching techniques. Parents will also have to continuously do research and adapt their teaching methods to make sure your kids receive the best standard of education. You need to prepare to be more patient and innovative in assisting a child who is a slow learner or who has special learning needs.

3. It causes financial restraints

Your spouse or you will have to either opt for a part-time job or not work at all so that one of you can guide the kids with their homeschooling. And considering that you need to buy books, computers, and other educational tools and activities, your list of expenses can get quite long.

4. It limits your child's opportunities to participate in team sports, competitions, and other extra-curricular activities

Socializing with kids the same age is one of the biggest challenges for homeschooled children. Parents try to solve this by scheduling play dates, organizing sports teams with other families who have homeschooled students, and other ways. However, their kids will still miss out on a large chunk of experiences that can make their school years more unforgettable, such as prom night, inter-school sports competitions, and school clubs.

6. It raises a lot of questions and sometimes even disapproval from other people

Even if more families are adopting homeschooling each year, most people still cannot fully understand

the concept of not letting your children go to a 'regular' school. It can get pretty tiring and frustrating to explain your reasons again and again. And it can even become annoying when others openly express their disapproval and bewilderment. Your kids can also be bullied by other kids because they are 'weird'. Some people will even question the intelligence or knowledge of your children because they think you can't learn properly if you don't learn in a traditional school setup.

If you think that you do not have the resources, patience, and dedication to successfully help your kids learn outside a public or private school environment, then homeschooling is not for you. And if you're discouraged by the current educational system of your country but can't home school your kids at the moment, remember that education doesn't have to be limited to schools. You can still find ways to help your kids learn the most effective way possible and ensure they get the education they deserve by providing them with supplemental classes at home or exposing them to the big, wide world of learning that exists outside their classroom.

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